

Riad Si Musa or Grand Riad

The Riad Si Musa is a prototype of the traditional architectural urban type of dwelling. It is the core of the Bahia Palace and its oldest part.

The Riad adopts a rectangular architectural layout (35m x 32m), with an open-air courtyard in the form of a quadripartite garden adorned with three white marble fountains. On the north wall, a crafted alcove was graciously fitted out using zellige, sculpted plaster and painted cedar wood roof. It served as a rest and relaxation area for the Vizir.

On the east and west sides are two oblong rooms preceded by a gallery superbly decorated with multi-coloured glass tiles. They are beautifully ornamented with floors made of marble pieces and zellige tiles, walls covered with zellige panels up to 1m60 delimited by a strip of sculpted plaster. In order to provide visual comfort and field balance, a bare part was deliberately left to be followed by a cedar wood ceiling carved with geometric, floral and epigraphic motifs in natural and sparkling colours.

In the northwest room, an alcove splendidly decorated. On its sculpted plaster frame, we can read two poetic verses in Arabic with a ciphered formula on the date of the construction of the palace (بشرى لنا): ا=1، ن=50، ل=30، ي=1، ر=200، ش=1000، ب=2، with a sum of 1284 Hegira, which corresponds to 1867-1868. It also entails the expression « son of Ahmed » which refers to the builder Musa Ben Ahmed Al-Cherki Al-Boukhari.